

Potassium Trihydroxyfluoborate

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In the literature a variety of fluoboric acids and salts have been described^{1,2}. But till now mono-fluotrihydroxyboric acid or its salts have not been reported.

The present authors have found that the solubility of various fluorides are increased in the presence of boric acid. The thermometric and conductometric titrations of the system $\text{KF}-\text{H}_3\text{BO}_3$ showed breaks in the ratio 1 : 1. From mixtures of potassium fluoride and boric acid, the present authors have been able to isolate a well-crystalline non-hygroscopic compound, which furnished the following analytical results: Found, K, 32.58; B, 9.21; F, 15.30%; K $[\text{BF}(\text{OH})_3]$ requires K, 32.61; B, 9.02; F, 15.85%.

The potassium salt could be recrystallised from water and stable in air. It is highly soluble in water. The salt furnished mix-crystals with potassium permanganate suggesting the isomorphism between the two salts.

Further work is in progress and details will be reported later.

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